

Citation and Reference Guidelines Use of GenAI in an Assignment

This document is completed by the teacher and is shared with the students with the guidelines for the assignment.

Course code:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Semester & year:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Teacher's name:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Title production:	Click or tap here to enter text.

Permitted level of use for this production

LEVEL 0	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4
<input type="checkbox"/>				
Prohibited Use	Limited use	Targeted use	Framed use	Free use

For the purpose of:

- Learning
- Language

Copyright information

If you are considering using a generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) tool in the production mentioned above, please consider the following:

- You are responsible for any content produced with or without GenAI that is included in your assignment.
- Content generated by AI tools may contain errors or falsehoods. Validation of the quality of responses is therefore doubly important.
- Under current Canadian copyright law, the content generated by AI tools is in the **public domain** because the GenAI tools are not recognized as authors under the law and the content generated does not meet the criteria of a protected work, particularly the criteria of originality.
- The company providing the services may have certain requirements in its **terms of use**. Since the algorithms and computer code belong to the company that developed them, it is important to take these provisions into account. These could also provide details on the reuse of submitted data (confidentiality).

How do I cite the use of GenAI in a production?

In the spirit of honest and responsible conduct, you must ALWAYS explicitly mention any use of artificial intelligence, in accordance with the [academic regulations](#) (9.4.1 Délits relatifs aux études). In addition, **for educational purposes, it is recommended to always integrate the prompts, as well as the full responses generated by the GenAI tools, into the assignment.** These can be integrated directly into the body of the text or as a footnote. Long answers may be included as an appendix to your document or in additional documents, depending on the teacher's instructions.

The following list includes the citation rules to be followed according to the type of content generated in APA style. Some adaptations can be made according to the style agreed for the submission of the work.

Scenarios	Citation rules
Bibliography	<p>For each GenAI used, add it to the bibliographic references at the end of your document, following these rules:</p> <p>Name of the entity that created the GenAI. (Date of version used). <i>Name of GenAI tool (version)</i> [additional descriptions]. URL</p> <p>Notes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The name of the GenAI tool serves as the title and is in italics.• The purpose of the text in square brackets is to briefly describe the type of model. Currently, GenAI is mostly a “large language model”.• In the event that the name of the publisher differs from that of the creator entity of the GenAI, it is necessary to place the publisher's name in front of the URL.• The URL provided must lead directly to the page from which the <i>chat</i> can be started. <p><i>Example</i></p> <p>OpenAI. (2024). <i>ChatGPT 4.0 mini</i> (Sept. 3 version) [large language model]. https://chat.openai.com/chat</p>
Single mention	<p>If this is a document-wide reference, insert the name of the tool (ChatGPT, Copilot, etc.), as well as the use you have made of it in the methodology or preliminary pages or final pages.</p> <p>The reference should then be included in the bibliography.</p> <p><i>Examples</i></p> <p>Some formulations of this production have been assisted by ChatGPT 4 (Sept. 3 version).</p> <p><i>Note: The teacher may ask you to write down each use directly in the text.</i></p> <p>The layout of this document was generated by Gamma (free version) and then adapted from the query “...”.</p> <p>This exercise was generated by Gemini (version 1.0) from the query “...”.</p> <p>Gemini (version 1.0) was used to develop a draft plan and organize the ideas in this document.</p>
Citation in the body of the text	<p>Any content generated by a GenAI tool must be cited in the text. This reference takes the form of an author-date citation (APA style), even if the generated element is technically in the public domain. The author is replaced by the creator of the GenAI.</p> <p>The reference should then be included in the bibliography.</p>

Scenarios	Citation rules
	<p>Direct Quote After the quotation, write, in parentheses, the name of the creator the GenAI, followed by the year of the version used:</p> <p><i>Example</i></p> <p>When the following query is submitted to ChatGPT: “Is ...” ?, the generated text indicates that “...”. (OpenAI, 2024).</p> <p>Paraphrase After paraphrasing, write, in parentheses, the name of the creator the GenAI, followed by the year of the version used:</p> <p><i>Example</i></p> <p>When the following query is sent to Perplexity: “Is ...” ?, the generated answer will indicate that [paraphrasing the answer in your own words] (Perplexity AI, 2024).</p>
Image	<p>For each image generated by an GenAI tool, write the reference below the image, including the prompt, followed by the full reference in the bibliography, or put the full reference, including the prompt, in a footnote. Refer to the bibliography citation rules explained above.</p> <p><i>Example of reference under the photo and in the bibliography</i></p> <p>Below the image: Image generated from the prompt “...”, by <i>Midjourney</i> (2024).</p> <p>In the bibliography: Midjourney. (2024). <i>Midjourney</i> (version 6) [large language model]. https://www.midjourney.com/home</p> <p><i>Example reference at the bottom of the page</i></p> <p>This image was generated from the prompt “...”.</p> <p>OpenAI. (2024). <i>DALL-E 3</i> (version 3) [large language model]. https://chat.openai.com/chat</p>
Computer code	<p>In the comments of the computer code, specify the GenAI’s tool that was used and the use you made of it, followed by the bibliographic reference. It is possible to annotate a section of code or the entire document.</p> <p><i>Example</i></p> <p>This section of the computer code was annotated by ChatGPT 4 and then adapted from the prompt “...”.</p> <p>OpenAI. (2024). <i>ChatGPT 4</i> (May 3 version) [large language model]. https://chat.openai.com/chat</p>

To go further: the sources of inspiration for this document

Bureau du droit d'auteur. (n.d.). *Intelligence artificielle*. Université Laval | Bibliothèque.
<https://www.bda.ulaval.ca/intelligence-artificielle/>

Collecto. (n.d.). *Outil bibliographique : Échange avec un agent conversationnel*. Diapason.
https://mondiapason.ca/fichiers/OutilBibliographique/#1_5_483

Les bibliothèques. (n.d.). *Citer œuvres et images en style APA (7^e éd.) : Image générée par IA*. Université de Montréal. <https://bib.umontreal.ca/citer/styles-bibliographiques/citer-oeuvres-images-style-apa?tab=5313522>

Les bibliothèques. (n.d.). *Citer selon les normes de l'APA, 7^e édition : En bibliographie (modèles)*. Université de Montréal. <https://bib.umontreal.ca/citer/styles-bibliographiques/apa?tab=5248896>

McAdoo, T. (2024, February 23). *How to cite ChatGPT*. APA Style. <https://apastyle.apa.org/blog/how-to-cite-chatgpt>

Service des bibliothèques et archives. (2024, May 6). *Intelligences artificielles : Rédaction et citation*. Université de Sherbrooke. <https://libguides.biblio.usherbrooke.ca/IA/redaction>

Unless otherwise noted, the content of this work is available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). You are encouraged to share and adapt it, according to the following condition, which is to attribute parenthood to the work.

Translated by Bowles, E. & Beaudet, M. (2024) from the original document by Cabana, M. et Beaudet, M. (2024). [Modèles de citations : utilisation de l'IA dans une production](#). Service de soutien à la formation, Université de Sherbrooke. Sous licence [CC BY 4.0](#).

The illustrations used in this document are inspired by vector images from the [Flaticon](#) website created by Yogi Aprellyanto, as well as Freepik. They have been personalized by the authors of this document.